

MEMS Tunable Meta-optics for High-efficiency Dynamic Light Field Manipulation

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Abstract—Recent advances in piezoelectric MEMS enabled multifunctional optical metasurfaces (OMSs) for dynamic phase and polarization control are presented. Moreover, theoretical investigations on the MEMS-OMS configuration show that control over scattering phase singularities in the parameter space determined by the MEMS-OMS separations and meta-atom sizes with the OMS, underpins these developments.

Dynamic optical metasurfaces (OMS) stand at the forefront of advancing intelligent optical systems and networks due to their ultra-compact design and reconfigurable responses [1]. The evolution of dynamic OMS has significantly benefited from the incorporation of active materials such as 2D materials, phase-change materials (PCMs), liquid crystals (LCs) and others [2]. However, challenges persist in achieving an optimal balance between speed and efficiency. For instance, while dynamic OMS using 2D materials offer rapid response times, they tend to have limited modulation strength. Conversely, dynamic OMS that integrate PCMs and LCs can attain high modulation strength but typically suffer from slower responses. Additionally, LC-based dynamic OMS encounter issues related to polarization dependence, presenting a critical area for further improvement.

In a recent breakthrough, we have developed a MEMS-OMS platform that synergizes a piezoelectric MEMS mirror with a plasmonic OMS. This innovative combination has led to a ultracompact system capable of dynamically manipulating reflection phase and polarization with high efficiency, substantial modulation strength, and rapid response (up to 100 kHz), as showcased in our demonstrations. We have successfully demonstrated a variety of dynamic optical functionalities, including blazed gratings [3, 4], focusing lenses [3], waveplates [5], as well as both linear and chiral polarizer [6, 7]. Recent advancements include: (1) the expansion to OMS stacks, enabling multi-level phase control for switching between distinct functions [8]; and (2) the integration of MEMS-OMS into laser cavities, facilitating mode-switchable vortex lasers [9].

Our investigation into the mechanism behind this dynamic response has unveiled that it stems from the controllable and tunable scattering phase singularities within a specific parameter space. This parameter space is defined by the MEMS-OMS separation and the dimensions of the meta-atoms. We have explored both tunable gap-surface-plasmon (GSP) resonances and hybrid plasmonic/Fabry-Pérot resonances to design the phase singularities within this parameter space.

To summarize, we will discuss the future outlooks for this platform, highlighting its potential to revolutionize the field of dynamic meta-optics with its innovative approach to achieving rapid, efficient, and strong modulation capabilities.

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